

THE HUMAN RIGHTS JOURNEY: MIGRATION THROUGH THE LENS OF INTERNATIONAL LAW

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Abstract

This paper explores the multifaceted nature of human rights risks inherent to migration agreements between the European Union (EU) and third countries under ICESCR framework. Cooperation agreements and bilateral readmission deals focusing on preventing irregular migration and strengthening border security lead to rights abuses such as retention, lack of access to essential commodities and services, and assault and exploitation by militias. The outsourcing of EU border checks often relocates migrants into States with poor human rights and/or the ability to protect them, thus, escalating their risks. The paper focuses on the EU Member States' extra-territorial obligations under the ICESCR and states that these should refrain from contributing to human rights abuses in other countries through migration policies. It reviews the legal approaches to the issues of extraterritoriality, non discrimination or the right to the adequate standard of living, stressing the idea of EU Member States' obligation to bring their policies in line with IHRL. Also, this paper discusses the problem of the scattered and uneven adherence to IHLs and other international human rights law instruments around the world, which creates various challenges in the full protection of migrants' rights. It is established that there is no direct focus on groups of migrant as a subject of distinctive precarious situations in the existing legal instruments, their treatment in the context of detention, access to health care and labor rights. In response to these issues, the paper suggests raising awareness, the synchronisation of the national legislation with the international human rights norms and standards, the promotion of international cooperation and the support, the recognition, and integration of the migrants' voice into influential policy mechanisms and processes. This way, the international

community can aim at improved and just protection of HRs for migrants and their equality and worth in any context.

Several legal authorities on this embargo include the Hirsi Jamaa and Others v. Italy, M. S. S. v. Belgium and Greece, and R (on the application of EM (Eritrea)) v. Secretary of State for the Home Department which show how judicial control is relevant to ensuring countries adhere to their commitments on rights of individuals in the contemporary world. Based on the analysis the paper recommends the following steps to enhance the protection of migrants' rights within the existing international instruments.

Keywords: Human rights, migration deals, European Union, ICESCR, extraterritorial obligations, non-refoulement, international cooperation, legal frameworks, migrant protection.

1. Introduction

Migration has always been an innate quality of human society an intrinsic characteristic of society of centuries. Mobility remains one of the most profound hallmarks of globalisation with millions of people travelling to different parts of the world in quest of improved livelihoods, shelter and a better future. However, migration is not easy over and there are several problems associated with the process one of which is protection of migrants. These rights are protected within the framework of international law, however, the exercise of those legal traditions proves quite challenging. Migration law is regulated within the framework of international law, based on general human rights treaties, conventions, and other sources of international law. Prominent among them are the Universal Declaration of Human Rights of 1948, the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights of 1966, and the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights of 1966 and the 1951 UN Refugee Convention and the 1967 protocol. All these instruments together uphold the rights of all persons, including the migrants regardless of their status in the country and or the world (UN General Assembly 1948; UN General Assembly 1966; UN General Assembly 1966; UNHCR 1951). Another principle which is fundamental in international migration law revolves around the non-refoulement where the return of persons to their home country is prohibited where they are likely to face threats to their lives or liberty (Goodwin-Gill & McAdam, 2007). This principle is critical to the protection of refugees and lies

within the 1951 Refugee Convention. Nevertheless, the practice of non-refoulement is not always carried out efficiently, especially when the directly affected state responsibility conflicts with sovereignty and national security (Hathaway, 2005). Despite the inherent difficulties in regulation, there are specific conventions that form part of the international legal framework on rights of Migrant Workers and Members of Their Families-International convention on the protection of the rights of all migrant workers and members of their families (UN General Assembly, 1990). It enlightens the states on the importance that they recognise the dignity of the migrant workers apart from the role they play in both the home and recipient nation economy.

Nevertheless, more comprehensive legal frameworks have not operating to effectively address rights for migrants. Governments seem reluctant to go the whole hog as regards the compliance with the set international standards, this is due to the increasing nationalism, xenophobia, and hardline immigration policies. For instance, detention for longer periods, no access to basic rights, such as education and healthcare, and exploitation in different forms may be a challenge that affects many migrants (Bosworth, 2014). These issues bring out a shocking reality of how we, as a society, have failed in enforcing laws that favor migration and instead subject migrants to torture. Migrants themselves as well as non-governmental human rights organisations can appeal to the international agencies, such as UNHCR and IOM that actively campaign for migrants' rights protection. Such organisations strive at achieving political cooperation, aiding in international policies implementation, and ensuring compliance with the international norms (Betts, 2011). They are instrumental in ensuring the adoption of the norms in law more practical and easily applicable in a society. When migration is supplemented by other challenges in the global arena including climate change issues and economic disparities, the migration issue becomes even more challenging to address. There is a definition of "climate refugees" who are people with the need to move from one area to another because of the changes in the climate and adverse effects of climatic events (McAdam, 2012). However, there is insufficient legal international standards to respond adequately to the problems associated with these migrants, requiring new directions and changes in policy and practice (Docherty & Giannini, 2009). The Agenda for Sustainable Development as well as the Global Compact for Safe, Orderly and

Regular Migration (GCM), endorsed in 2018, exemplify a progress in the approach to understand the complex dynamic of migration (UN General Assembly, 2018). The GCM adopted principles for which it encourages international cooperation and an international approach to migration such as the need to respect the rights of migrants, to promote legal well – established pathways for migration and addressing factors fuelling irregular migration. Even if the GCM is not legally binding, its existence shows the worldwide opinion on the proper regulation of migration that requires collective actions.

2. History

Population mobility has been a core part of the lives of people as early as in prehistory, and different moves influenced the whole world. People in early stages of their evolution used to migrate mostly in response to availability of food, favorable climatic conditions and to escape from calamities and wild beasts. As states and societies evolved over time, migration was not only enhanced but also assumed an economical, political, and sometimes even religious manner. Understanding of these dynamics is critical for appreciating the historical development of the field of international law as it responds to the complex nature of human mobility and protection of migrants' rights.

2.1 The Paleanthropology and Precolonial Era

The first migration of pre-historic humans started about 60,000 years ago and would later see humans' colonising the entire globe. These ones were mainly as an escape of some sort of these early settlers were mainly in search of resources and existence. With the onset of agriculture approx 10,000 years ago, people put down roots in specific areas, but did not necessarily remain in one place permanently, prehistoric migrations took place in response to factors such as climate and population pressure. At the early periods of the world's history, migrations ended up being connected with economic relations, wars, and the occurrence of colonisation. For instance, the Roman Empire experienced considerable migration processes as people in the territory, as well as in other countries, moved due to the efficient infrastructure that connected domains through the thick web of Roman roads and other passages for trade. Ancient migration was caused by profiteers such as merchants, military personnel, and captives such as slaves, and movements resulting from the effects of wars and conquests. Such movements were regulated by some of the most primitive legal

instruments, which were rather severe in their treatment of individuals moving across borders without proper authorisation and providing for the rights of migrants in a minimalistic way.

2.2 From Middle Ages to the Early Modern Period

During the Middle Ages, there are evidences about Asians, Africans, and America migrating to other parts of the world due to the spread of different beliefs and religions like; the spread of Islam and Christianity, and the crusades which resulted to major movements of people in Europe and the middle east. In this talking there were also other movements including the trans-Saharan slave trade later followed by the Atlantic slave trade which saw millions of Africans moved from their original homes to America's. The European colonialism with was defined by the Age of Exploration commenced from the early modern period and saw colonisation of almost all corners of the globe. This period also saw mobility and transportation of the European populations to new colonies, while at the same time indigenous people of these areas were displaced or wiped out. The most. write devastating process of migration in the history of human civilisation was the transatlantic slave trade which saw millions of African people sold and transported like goods to the American continent under oppressive conditions.

2.3 19th and Early 20th Centuries

This led to industrialisation and colonisation, these are processes that have significant impacts on societies since they alter the ways in which human beings carry out their economic activities. Industrialisation along with colonisation processes were some of the main factors influencing migration in the 19th and early 20th centuries. Urbanisation process in Europe and North America led to a need for employment and a large number of immigrants flocked to find work in these cities from surrounding countryside and from other countries. This period also saw the Great Migration of black people from the rural productive South to the urban areas in the North to look for job opportunities in industries that were fast growing and to escape oppression by the discriminating whites. European colonialism remained an important force in the management and organisation of mobility for labour in international contexts, using indigenous and migratory labour in their empires. For viz., Indian and Chinese inductions were crucial for manning plantations and construction activities across Africa Caribbean and South East Asia

for Britain's empire. Such migrations were controlled by colonial laws that offered the Canary Islander workers little rights and protections.

2.4 Post-World War II Era

The period after the Second World War can be considered as the period of the transition to the legal regulation of migration on the international level. The decision of displacement of numerous populations during and after the war increased the pressure of international organisations in terms of protection on refugees and displaced people. The UN was formed in 1945 and in the same year, the International Bill of Human Rights was signed, and later, in 1948 the UDHR was adopted. In spite of the fact that, migration was not topical at the formation of UN, some rights for migrant were protected. This came into fruition when in 1951, the Convention Relating to the Status of Refugees also known as the Refugee Convention, provided fundamental standards of treatment that states are to follow in relation to refugees and the principle of non-refoulement, the protection from refoulement of refugees. This convention coupled with it's the 1967 protocol remains the core reference for the protection of refugees to date (UNHCR, 1951). The two International covenants; The ICCPR and the ICESCR formulated in 1966 provided stronger layer of human rights, that applies to everybody including the migrants (UN General Assembly 1966; UN General Assembly 1966).

2.5 Late 20th and Early 21st Centuries

The last quarter of twentieth century and the twenty first century have witnessed upheaval in migration due to globalisation factors, economic differences, issues related to conflict, and environmental factors. Technological advancement and ease of transport systems also played an important role in the promotion of liberalisation with the easing of political barriers that come with the war and opening up of neoliberal economic reforms. But such movements also gave rise to unprecedented problems such as, asylum seekers control and regulation, human trafficking, and legal protection of migrant workers. The ICMW came into force in 2000, specifically to address the rights of all migrant workers and members of their families, regardless of skill level and duration of their stay at the destination country (UN General Assembly, 1990). Nonetheless, even though the ICMW is in some ways a follow up

to the GC, it has been ratified by a limited number of countries, illustrating that the enhancement of the methods of protection for migrants remains a work in progress. The new phenomenon that has characterised the 21st century is also the issue of climate change and the new challenges that it has brought concerning migration. Pollution and climate change effects have also heightened forced mass displacement due to effects such as floods, cyclones as gives rise to the climate refugees (McAdam, 2012). However, present state and international legal systems fail to respond to the needs of these migrants adequately and there is a need to develop new approaches and solutions (Docherty & Giannini, 2009, p. 6).

2.6 Recent Developments

Due to these dynamics and changes in processes of migration, the Global Compact for Safe, Orderly and Regular Migration was developed in 2018. The GCM is a remarkable shift towards advancing a global partnership on migration and describes a more comprehensive and coherent. It continues to call for partnerships for effective cooperation, refugee and migrant's rights, and dealing with the root causes of irregular migration (UN General Assembly, 2018). While aspirational, the GCM represents the acknowledgment of states across the globe that the migration process should be well-managed and conducted humanely. The migrations of people from one region to another are a clear indicator of the drive inside every human being and the struggles they go through in search of better living conditions and safety. However, the dynamics of international law on migration have changed with time to cater to this complexity, given that migration is not only a global movement of people but also entails important human rights for individuals. When Garry Martin discusses the challenges of comparative analysis, he also points to this issue as a major concern. To fill this void, the world needs more cooperation, more calls for human rights and for adherence to them, as well and more need for flexibility in the legal solutions when new problems of migration appear. The above historical narrative supports the necessity of protecting the human rights of migrants from the inception of their journey to the terminal point, as a portrayal of the humane perspective towards migration.

3. Literature Review

- a) Pijnenburg (2023) analyses the articles of the International Covenant on Economic, Social, and Cultural Rights (ICESCR) to scrutinise possible human rights violations of migration deals in the framework of the EU Member States' obligations. It seeks to analyse whether the states have obligations for individuals in third countries regarding migration agreements. Pijnenburg notes that such supply chains are associated with extensive human rights abuses, as border security is outsourced, and people are put in precarious positions with minimal representation (Pijnenburg, 2023). The evaluation gives rise to conflict between the sovereignty of the state and the functioning of an international human rights approach in management of migration and shows that EU's practices do not conform to Article 2(2) of the ICESCR non-discrimination and Article 11 of right to adequate standard of living.
- b) Bahri (2022) analyses the characteristics and reasons for international migrations by means of the database of the Mixed Migration Center (2019) and other Mexican Government data (2016). On their part, economic influences, contending and persecution emerge as core causes of migration from the study. Bahri highlights some of the difficulties in advancing human rights in the face of such migration phenomena. The ecosystems indicate that there are gaps in existing law systems at the international level that failed to address the various aspects of migration and protect the rights of immigrants (Bahri, 2022). The study wants the global society to come up with a fresh and different perspective on how the socio-economic statuses of the migrants can be acknowledged as well as the states to be encouraged to cooperate in the protection of human rights.
- c) Slack (2022) offers a detailed analysis of the topic and international human rights law with an emphasis on migration. Exploring the UN human rights systems' limitations and derogations we present this book chapter that focuses on the work and function of treaty bodies, the Human Rights Council and the Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights. Slack traces several examples in separate passages to elaborate on the difficulties of implementing human rights in relation to migration. The chapter posits that indeed, the UN system, though, provides ways by which human rights violations can be addressed, the implementation of such remedial measures is

wanting, especially when it comes to migrant populations as such persons grapple with numerous challenges in the quest for justice (Slack, 2022). Based on this analysis, it is revealed that enhancing these mechanisms and applying better international cooperation remain crucial for enhancing human rights in aspects related to migrants.

4. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

This paper presents and discusses the following research question:

1. What is the main focus of criticism in relation to European migration deals with third countries?
2. In what measure and to what extent can EU Member States be bound under the ICESCR towards migrants in third countries due to these deals?
3. What are the forces preferring international migration, and what kind of tendencies appear from these forces, economical, social and political?
4. Examining the workplace, what can be said about the efficiency of the UN human rights mechanisms in the context of violations of migrants' rights, and what amendments, if any, can be made to improve the situation?
5. How does state sovereignty influence the conflict between migratory control and the safeguarding of human rights, with specific reference to international treaties?
6. How can international cooperation be improved in order to ensure the protection of migrants' rights on one hand and to meet state legitimate concern of managing migration flows on the other?
7. Where are some successful and/or non-successful uses/moments of international human rights law in the case of migrants and what can be observed from those experiences?

5. Human Rights Implications Arising From The Trade in Immigration Agreements Between The EU and Third Countries

The negotiations of migration relations between the EU and the third countries largely contain critical human rights issues related to the treatment and protection of Migrants in the transit/transfer or asylum countries. Such arrangements, which are focused on preventing migrants' irregular entry into other countries and improving border security, may result in situations that negatively affect migrants, including potential torture, detention, restricted rights to necessary goods and services, and violence. For example the EU-Turkey deal signed in march 2016 aimed at discouraging refugees and migrants to flood Europe's borders acknowledged putting refugees in detention centres in heavily congested and congesting Greece where medical attention and shelter and even reliable legal aid are scarce. Likewise, the EU's bilateral cooperation agreements with Libya have been criticised for enabling migrant interception and forced return to Libya where migrants suffer from human rights abuses such as, arbitrary arrest, torture, and forced labor (Pijenburg, 2023). The process frequently leads to migrants' being relocated to countries with lower levels of human rights observance and mean capabilities of guaranteeing their subjects' welfare. Libya, Niger and Sudan for instance are countries that the EU is now relying on to help control migration; these countries Presidentials are not known to be welcoming towards human rights thus migrants' rights in those countries are not well protected legally. For example, in Libya there is no effective government and conflict continues that is why migrants remain at very high risk unable to seek asylum or to get justice for violated rights. Therefore, such agreements can worsen the position of the population and situations when human rights are violated actively. However, these agreements are frequently coupled with financial and organisational providing of third countries with tools for strict migration regulation that allows to question ethical stance of EU in possible violations. For example, EU donated funds and carried out training of the Libyan Coast Guard, whose task is to intercept migrants to Libya to bring them back and yet data about torture on Libyan migrants is well documented. This raises questions as to the compliance of EU states with the international human rights laws and in particular the non-refoulement principle that entrants that it is unlawful to return anyone to a country where they are likely to be subjected to torture, inhuman and or degrading treatment, or to be otherwise abused of their rights. Furthermore, these deals might be also problematic in the context of the different international human

rights laws and standards. According to the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) every individual has the right to seek and to obtain, in other countries, asylum from persecution. Also, the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR) and International Covenant on Economic, Social, and Cultural Rights (ICESCR) provide that states have commitments on rights of all persons in their territory and under their control, including migrants. In addition, according to the U. N Refugees' 1951 Convention and its 1967 protocol, refugees themselves should not be punished for having entered the hosting state unlawfully or stay there unlawfully, and should never be expelled to a country where their life or liberty is in danger.

However, such rights are not protected even during the implementation of the agreements on migration because of the violation of the mentioned legal frameworks. For instance, concerning the EU-Libya deal, the EU funding and cooperation with Libyan authorities have been condemned for disregarding the principle of non-refoulement especially because migrants intercepted by the Libyan Coast Guard are repatriated to detention camps where they are tortured and, in some cases, die. Likewise, the EU-Turkey deal has been discussed regarding its legal basis under the international and European legal asylum law due to the idea of seeking asylum in Turkey which is a third safe country according to EU, without proper attentiveness apropos such issues as its inability to offer necessary safeguard as well as risk of refoulement where individuals could be persecuted and experience severe hardships. Therefore, examination of these worries is essential for comprehending the potential impact of such approaches to the management of migration in third countries as violation of the citizens' rights and their dignity. However, precise analysis of such deals is highly necessary to check the legal and ethically proper regulation of migration policies and their compliance with human rights and commitments of the recipient countries based on the norms of international law. In this regard, policymakers should endeavor to come up with a rightful compact on migration and refugee that meeting and respect human rights, safe and legal passage to migrants besides ensuring that migrants to be accorded respect and dignity while in the country or awaiting a chance to transit to another country regardless of their legal status or origin.

6. Obligations of EU Member States Under the ICESCR towards Migrants in Third Countries

The International Covenant on Economic, Social, and Cultural Rights (ICESCR) overviews different commitments on its state parties in executing the economic, social, and cultural rights of every beneficiary within its territorial jurisdiction. These obligations are disclosed in a number of articles of the ICESCR, including but not limited to Article 2, to which each State Party is bound to undertake measures, both domestically and International assistance and cooperation to progressively realise the Covenant. But when EU Member States get involved in migration arrangements that impact persons in third countries, issues of extra-territoriality of these rights emerge. There is a growing understanding of the ETOs under the ICESCR that basically require that states ensure the protection of individual rights in the external environment especially where such impacts are reasonably foreseeable. As per Article 2(1) of the ICESCR, the states are required to act individually, as well as collectively through international cooperation and assistance and achieve the purpose of the Covenant, that is, the rights enumerated in it. This also entails guaranteeing that their activities such as migration polices and agreements do not lead to human rights abuses in third countries. For example, the ICESCR in its Article 11 outlines the right of everyone to a minimum core essential supply of food, clothing, shelter, and the right to the enhancement of one's living standards and conditions. Thus, the EU Member States must make sure that the conclusion of bilateral/multilateral agreements on migration does not result in the persons falling into the category of migrants being deprived of the above-listed rights. Likewise, the ICESCR in Article 12 recognises the right to the highest level of physical and mental health, which imposes on states' responsibility to uphold actions that may lead to the emergence of health crises or decline the level of health of individuals in third countries.

The identification of the scope of such obligations requires the examination of legal implementation of the extraterritoriality issues, non-discrimination, and right to adequate living standard. To supplement the legal arguments of ETO, there are guidelines from the various human rights instruments or bodies. Maastricht Principles on Extraterritorial Obligations of States in the Area of Economic, Social

and Cultural Rights – the list of conditions that define the extraterritorial obligations for states, was developed in 2011 by international law experts. Principle 8, for instance, states that a state has obligations to respect, protect, and fulfill economic, social, and cultural rights in three circumstances. This means that the state's responsibilities exist when it has the power to control the human rights within that area; when the actions the state takes can reasonably be expected to impact on the enjoyment of these rights in other areas; and where the state is in a position to control or significantly influence another state or is able to help another state meet its obligations. Analysing the meaning of the obligations provided for in the ICESCR may track how the EU migration policies can be made fully compliant with human rights frameworks. For instance, in the case of *Hirsi Jamaa and Others v. Italy (2012)* : ECHR, Section 4, the European Court of Human Rights has declared that states cannot expel a person to a country in which they will be in danger of being subjected to inhuman or degrading treatment. This principle corresponds to the non-refoulement principle of international human rights law in which individuals are not to be returned to a country where they may face persecution and their right to life and liberty may be at risk. The following legal considerations support this regards as it relates to migration deals; it is pertinent that they must not breach the ICESCR and other treaties on human rights or the rights of recipient countries' people.

In addition, the Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (CESCR) that is responsible for supervising the parties' compliance with the ICESCR noted in the General Comment No. 14 right to health and General Comment No. 19 right to social security the states should regulate the impact of their policies and actions on the enjoyment of the rights in other countries. This means that EU Member States should conduct a critical examination of the effects of its migration cooperation agreements on human rights of migrants in third countries to avoid negation of rights to health, adequate standard of living as well as social security among others. Thus, the analysis of Extraterritorial Obligations within EU Member State concerning the ICESCR presupposes examination of the international legal norms and their interpretation. This requires the accordance of the policies of migration with the objectives of international cooperation and aid, principles of non-discrimination and economic, social and cultural rights. Thus, when EU

Member States act in this manner it will advance their capabilities to adhere to their international human rights legal requirements thereby enhancing the chances of a fair and humane international migration system.

7. Economic Social and Political Influences on International Migration

Migration in the international context is a multifaceted process that is generally characterised by several economic, social and/or political factors that lead individuals to migrate. Thus, social factors that include poor economic conditions in home country like poverty, unemployment and poor economic opportunities push people to seek better fortunes elsewhere. Other reasons that can be attributed to migration include social factors which include family reunion, education prospects and culture. Pressure from political factors like war, asylum or any political pressure may compel people to seek asylum in other countries in bid to seek protection. Essentials such as the above drivers necessitate data collection and research to have adequate knowledge on trends and motivation. For example, Mixed Migration Center Dataset (2019) as well as the data provided by the Mexican Government (2016) describe the main directions of migration and its causes. Analysing this data contributes to monitoring migration movements and the socio-economic environments that influence such movements, the need to acknowledge the underlying causes of migration and ensure the protection of migrants' rights (Bahri, 2022).

8. Difficulties and Opportunities in Promoting Human Rights Under Contemporary Sources of International Law

The rights of migrants as human beings are whose rights are violated pose formidable barriers in the present international legal systems. There are several outlined frameworks concerning migrants, and they present several gaps though they are well developed. To a large extent one of the difficulties with the general infringement on the dissemination of international human rights law is the diversity and uneven implementation of these laws from one jurisdiction to another. (Bahri, 2022) paper explains that migrants have limited rights to justice as well

as adequate protection because the level of implementation of the different international norms varies from country to country. For example, the 1951 Refugee Convention and the 1967 protocol offer a legal document for the protection of refugees, but the rates at which these countries implement the provisions and rights for refugees are different resulting in differential protection of refugees.

Overlapping legal orientations are further confounded by the absence of provisions in other current international legal appliances targeting migrants' predicament. Detention conditions, healthcare, and labor rights are some of the most important and sensitive aspects concerning migrants in which they feel the impact of discriminative measures most keenly. For instance, even though the International Convention on the Protection of the Rights of All Migrant Workers and Members of Their Families (ICMW) enhances the migrants' rights, it has not been ratified by many developed countries that serve as the migrants' destination. Together with the Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, this Convention highlights states' responsibilities to provide and protect people from living in squalor, to ensure their access to healthcare facilities, and prevent people from being exploited. However, in real life, economic and social rights are often violated or poorly realised as it has been mentioned by Committee on Migrant Workers in their periodic report (Committee on Migrant Workers, 2017). Furthermore, the bodies that regulate status and rights of migrants tend to fail in addressing and protecting gender-sensitive issues on the migrant women and children. Female migrants face a lot of horrendous situations like GVA, trafficking, and exploitation while they are migrating. The International human rights instruments – CEDAW and the CEDAW General Recommendation No. 26 address concerns about women migrant workers and the requirement for an array of progressive policies that respect women's rights. Thus, despite the adoption of the aforementioned recommendations, the actual protection of women migrants is still not consistent (Freedman, 2016). Less privileged children, particularly the ones isolated from their parents, are at extremely high risk of getting trafficked, abused, or denied education and health care. The CRC article 19 called for provisions to be made to protect children, although the provisions and the compliance differ from one country to another (UNICEF, 2018). To build on these frameworks, there is the need for a legal reform agenda together with international cooperation and the

adoption of the migrants' point of view in the formulation of policies. Legal liberalisation should therefore be directed at seeking to ensure the domestic legislation of sovereign states are in compliance with the provisions on the protection of migrants' rights under international law. This encompasses measures in the form of enforceable guidelines touching on issues such as detention, health care and employees' rights. Besides, the International cooperation should be improved in order to combat the cross-border threats including trafficking and smuggling which are required to prevent by the multilateral collaboration of the countries of origin, in transit, and the final countries of destination. For example, regional associations and architecture, including the EU CEAS represent the common set of asylum policies and practices among Member States that still faces the issue of developing the unified standards and practices (European Commission, 2020).

Policy formulation for and engagement with migrants should involve the consideration of the migrants' views to prevent the formulation of wrong policies. Migrant associations and activist organisations directly relate to this function because they can offer information and advice resulting from their own migratory experience. For instance, the Global Compact for Safe, Orderly and Regular Migration adopted in 2018 states that migrants' contributions should be recognised by involving them in the policy-making processes and IAS large and protect their rights (UN General Assembly, 2018). Meanwhile, overcoming these obstacles the international community can contribute to the improvement of the human rights situation of migrants. This includes not only the improvement of legislators or legal texts but also work on the capacity of the institutions that shall implement these legislations or texts. Education and human resource development for law enforcement agencies, judicial and other officials engaged in migration-related issues are essential to guarantee the respect of migrants' rights in practice. Moreover, regular assessment of the existing policies and measures to implement the protection of human rights for migrants is needed to find out any deficiencies and make necessary adjustments for the improvement of human rights for migrants. Hence, it is pertinent to state that though more efforts are being made throughout the year to hammer out the international legal standards regarding the rights of the migrants still more work is to be done in laying down mechanisms for their implementation and enforcement. Solving these issues presupposes

complex measures based on the legal regulation, international cooperation, and recognition of the migrant's active participation in the process of formation of the legal state. In this way, the rights and dignity of migrants would be more protected through the international communitarianism where they would be honoured with due respect despite their unlawful stay in another country or country of origin where they belong.

9. Effectiveness of United Nations Human Rights Mechanisms in Addressing Migrants' Rights Violations

The United Nations mechanisms under the domain of promoting human rights protection in the field, both in the legal and political sense, are rendered by treaty bodies, Human Rights Council, and the Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights that also addresses the violations recipients exerted on the migrants' rights. These mechanisms are aimed at addressing human rights situations and producing reports and recommendations on them worldwide. However, several factors hinder their ability to protect migrants rights to the desired level Here are main factors affecting effectiveness of human rights agencies in protection of migrants rights. For instance, the ability to compel the full obedience to the set human rights standards is not equal to all members. Besides, political interests and lack of resources sometimes can hinder these mechanisms to respond adequately to rights violation. Nevertheless, the UN system has accomplished advancing migrants' rights as an agenda and increasing awareness about violations of their rights. For those to be effective it is important that these mechanisms be strengthened through increased funding, political commitment and formal and stronger cooperation at the international level. In that sense, this approach can facilitate the protection of migrants' rights and monitor the states' compliance with the provisions of the international law (Slack, 2022).

10. State Sovereignty Versus Human Rights Protection in Migration Management

Thus, the state sovereignty has a critical position in the regulation of migration process and regularly can cause conflict with the human rights protection. On matters of control of the entry and stay of non-nationals in any given state, it is the states' sovereign rights that acts as the

controlling agent in matters regarding migration policies. Yet, such sovereign power needs to be exercised in conjunction with the necessity to adhere to the international human rights norms. Migration management that reflects securitisation approach affects negative human rights mainly because it strengthens border control measures which in turn encroach on migrants' rights including arbitrary detention of migrants, denial of asylum, and inadequate protection of vulnerable migrants. This tension is especially apparent in migration control which shifts border control responsibilities to the countries of origin and transitory, which have the weak human rights records. Such analysis requires considering the points of law and justice of the migration policies as well as their compatibility with the international human rights standards. In this regard, it is possible for the policymakers to find out the ways and means of migration management which is indeed compatible with sovereignty rights of states and can also defend the rights of individual migrants (Pijnenburg, 2023).

11. Enhancing International Cooperation For Better Migrant Rights Protection

Strengthening partnerships between states is necessary for preserving the human rights of migrants and at the same time for states' concerns related to migration management. First, cooperation can be described as the strategic working together of states, IOs, civil society, for formulating and implementing structural migration policies to safeguard migrants' human rights. This entails exchanging of experiences, offering technical and financial assistance to countries of destination, asylum, and transit and developing patterns of cooperation and communication. Multilateral cooperation, and specific conventions like the Global Compact for Migration, are frameworks for such cooperation set on the idea of joint responsibility and accountability. Enhancing these collaborative efforts may enable the reduction of the causes of migration, enhance the protection of migrants in transit and country of destination as well as the promotion of migration policies that are compliant with human rights principles. When coordinated, the international community will be able to effectively address the compounded issues of migration as well as improve the status of migrants' human rights (Bahri, 2022).

12. Case Studies For Participation in International Human Rights Protect Migrants

Explaining the experience of adopting and applying IHL in the protection of migrants, case studies are always helpful in understanding which interventions worked and which did not. That is why these examples demonstrate the real-world cases of the legal frameworks' usage and the potential issues and future enhancements. For example, analysing situations of migrants in countries with progressive migration policies on the preservation of rights can identify strategies. However, upon reviewing cases in which migrants have experienced substantial rights violation including-detention or asylum rejection, then, a gap in the legal system's defence and implementation could be highlighted? With such cases, policy makers as well as practitioners can learn lessons that would help in enhancing the status of the protection of human rights for migrants. Besides, such analysed case studies may also offer empirically backed suggestions for improving international law and increasing the measurability and effectiveness of states' human rights responsibilities (Slack, 2022).

I. Hirsi Jamaa and Others v. Italy, Application No. 27765/09, European Court of Human Rights, Judgment of 23 February 2012

This case focused on the Italian authorities' practice of interception of migrants on the high seas and the subsequent transfer of migrants back to Libya. The European Court of Human Rights determined that Italy failed to abide by the European Convention on Human Rights which requires that any form of treatment that leads to inhuman or degrading treatment is prohibited (Article 3) and that collective expulsion of non-nationals is prohibited (Protocol No. 4, Article 4). The Court recollect some of its key principles such as the principle of non-refoulement which bars the transferees from being sent back to their home country.

II. M.S.S. v. Belgium and Greece, Application No. 30696/09, European Court of Human Rights, Judgment of 21 January 2011

In this case, Applicant sought asylum in Belgium however before the Belgian authorities could consider his application for refugee status, he was expelled to Greece where he was ill-treated as a foreigner leading to the European Court of Human Rights ruling that Belgium as well as Greece breached the Applicant's rights under the European Convention

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on Human Rights. Greece was found to have inhuman and degrading treatment which amounted to the applicant being detained in poor conditions without proper or adequate reception facilities. Belgium was considered as directly responsible for confronting the applicant to such conditions by transferring him from Belgium to Greece in accordance with the Dublin Regulation while being aware of the flaws in the Greek system of asylum.

III. R (on the application of EM (Eritrea)) v. Secretary of State for the Home Department [2014] UKSC 12

The kind of removal to other European countries using the Dublin a regulation was determined by the UK Supreme court. The case particular being an Eritrean asylum seeker, she would be subjected to inhuman or degrading treatment if transferred to Italy. The Court relying on the article stated that the UK cannot expel asylum seekers to state where there is tangible chance that they shall have their human rights infringed the main issue being the state/ countries in which the asylum seeker shall be relocated.

IV. Al-Skeini and Others v. United Kingdom, Application No. 55721/07, European Court of Human Rights, Judgment of 7 July 2011

This case increase the application of the European Convention of Human Rights beyond the territory of the Member States. Thus, the European Court of Human Rights stated that the UK is accountable for the human rights abuses carried out by its forces in Iraq. Thus, the Court concluded that the UK's jurisdiction covered the acts performed by its soldiers and that the UK was, thus, to guarantee the protection of human rights even in foreign territories. This case holds importance to the infliction of the ETOs and the application of IHLR.

V. K.R.S. v. United Kingdom, Application No. 32733/08, European Court of Human Rights, Decision of 2 December 2008

In this case, the European Court of Human Rights covered the possibility of sending an Iranian asylum seeker from the UK to Greece based on the Dublin Regulation. The applicant stated that if he is deported to the Greece he will receive inhuman and degrading treatment because of shortcomings in the Greek asylum system. Again the court did not see the violation in this case, but cast its strong beliefs on states to

contemplate the circumstances in the receiving state and endeavor not to make deportations that would lead to human rights abolition.

VI. *Sale v. Haitian Centers Council, Inc.*, 509 U.S. 155 (1993)

On the case regarding the U. S and the interdiction of Haitian refugees on the high seas and their return to Haiti without a hearing, the United States Supreme Court made its ruling . The Court ruled that per the Refugee Convention one cannot rely on the non-refoulement principles to actions conducted outside the territories of Contracting States in this case on the high seas. This measure became one of the most discussed and telling examples of how the enforcement of the human rights protection across the borders can be quite problematic.

Conclusion

This paper analyses the human rights issues connected to the processes of migration cooperation between the European Union (EU) and third countries and establishes the problems that arise from the perspective of protection of migrants' rights within the framework of present-day international law. Such deals mean that migrants experience poor standards, forced detentions, restricted rights, and are exposed to other vices as was observed in the EU-Turkey and EU Libya deals. The minimum standards to extraterritorial obligations in the framework of the EU Member States on the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR) demonstrates the need for states to ensure that they do not transmit rights abuses through their migration policies in other countries. European Union legislation on extraterritoriality, non-discrimination, and the guarantee of the right to an adequate standard of living shows that it is necessary for EU Member States to level up the actions with the level of international human rights. In addition, because the implementation of international human rights law differs and is inconsistent across different jurisdictions, the protection of migrants' rights is also challenging. Due to the absence of adequate provisions within the legally binding acts regarding migrant's specific needs when it comes to detention, health facilities, and labour rights, legal developments are required on a much broader level and the international cooperation should be stepped up. This paper argues that it is necessary for migrants to participate in policy formulation so as to establish relevant and efficient policies. Thus, the case laws like *Hirsi*

Jamaa and Others v. Italy, M. S. S. v. Belgium and Greece, and R (on the application of EM (Eritrea)) v. Secretary of State for the Home Department highlight the powerful check and balance, namely, the judicial supervision over the states' compliance with their international obligations on human rights protection. These scenarios give understanding to the principle of non-refoulement and the necessity of prevention of expulsion of migrants to the countries where they may get subjected to severe human rights abuses.

Suggestions

I. Harmonize National and International Legal Standards: Harmonize National and International Legal Standards:

The first process towards improving the situation of migrants is the maximisation of protection of their rights is the process of approximating national legislation to international norms and standards. EU Member States should begin the process of acceding and/or implementing the ICESCR into their individual internal laws at the earliest. This involves the implementation measures ensuring that the country's and/or regional immigration policies and cooperation meet the principle of non-refoulement and have appropriate mechanisms against human rights abuses. There is a need to work on the adoption of the law reforms that pertain to the formulation of easy to implement including and not limited to, health, shelter, and freedom from exploitation of migrants.

II. Enhance International Cooperation and Support: Enhance International Cooperation and Support:

Enhancing partnership is important in tackling migration related issues, which has become an international affair through adherence to pulls across the world by recognising the rights of human being. Member States of the EU should scale up cooperation with countries of origin, transit and destination with a view to improving convening, strategic approaches to managing migration with a focus on respecting the rights of migrants. This accounts offering technical and financial assistance towards enhancement of third countries' effectiveness in the fight against migrants' rights abuse and inhumane treatment. Further more, regional structures for the asylum policies and practices like the Common European Asylum System within the European Union also need to be

strengthened because the differences between the states' practices are vast.

III. Incorporate Migrants' Perspectives in Policy-Making: Incorporate Migrants' Perspectives in Policy-Making:

Thus, the experience and voices of migrants should be included to establish responsible migration policies. Policy makers should seek to meet and consult with organisations and advocacy group which are led by migrants to know the exact difficulties and requirements of these migrants. This kind of participation can assist in making sure that the policies they are coming up with are informed by the challenges that migrants go through hence being more effective in addressing the vulnerabilities of migrants. In addition, the migrants' active participation through discussions and feedback ensures that the effects of these policies are constantly checked, and corrected where necessary, for the enhancement of the migrants' human rights.

By following the above-stated recommendations, the peoples of the world shall be in a better position to enhance the protection of human rights of migrant persons, and their promotion and protection regardless of place and situation.

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